

ABU ALI IBN SINA ON A CRITICAL - BIOGRAPHICAL ESSAY**Shoira Akhmedova**

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Abstract. *The article discusses the critical-biographical essay of the writer S.Ayni dedicated to Abu Ali ibn Sina and the image of the great encyclopedic scientist created in it. Many scientific, literary and artistic works have been written about the life and work of Abu Ali Ibn Sina, the founder of medical science, and his scientific heritage. In particular, a number of stories, short stories and novels dedicated to this encyclopedic scholar have been written and are being written in Uzbek literature. At the same time, it is possible to acknowledge that the critical-biographical essay, which gives full information about the life and work of the great scientist, was written by the great writer S. Ayni.*

Keywords: *essay, criticism, image, literary criticism, Shaykhur-raï, XX century, genres.*

АБУ АЛИ ИБН СИНА О КРИТИКО-БИОГРАФИЧЕСКОМ ОЧЕРКЕ

Аннотация. *В статье рассматривается критико-биографический очерк писателя С.Айни, посвященный Абу Али ибн Сине, и созданный в нем образ великого ученого-энциклопедиста. О жизни и деятельности основоположника медицинской науки Абу Али ибн Сины и его научном наследии написано много научных, литературных и художественных произведений. В частности, в узбекской литературе написан и пишется ряд рассказов, рассказов и романов, посвященных этому ученому-энциклопедисту. В то же время можно признать, что критико-биографический очерк, дающий полную информацию о жизни и деятельности великого ученого, написан великим писателем С. Айни.*

Ключевые слова: *очерк, критика, образ, литературоведение, Шайхур-райс, XX век, жанры.*

INTRODUCTION.

The great ruler, philosopher, scholar, great judge, talented writer and poet Abu Ali ibn Sino is an encyclopedic scholar who has played an important role in the history of the development of world science and culture. The biography of Abu Ali ibn Sina in the critical essay, which begins with the description, "The name of this great sage, known in Europe as Avicenna, is Husayn bin Abdullah bin bin Sina, Abu Ali ibn Sina is his kuniya, and Shaykhur-raï is his scientific nickname." Before talking about the works he left behind, the scholar thinks about the period in which he lived, the political, social environment, the Samanid dynasty.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Based on S. Aini's critical-biographical essay "Shaykhur-raï Abu Ali ibn Sino", the method of analytical analysis was used.

The genre of critical-biographical essays goes in this direction, which provides information about the life and work of the writer or poet, the literary environment to which he belongs, the history of creation, content, quality, place in the literary-historical process. Ibn Sina's parents, the sciences he learned in his childhood, give information that he was educated in the hands of Abu Abdullah Bakhiliy, a scholar of logic. After studying logic, wisdom, theology,

geometry, astronomy, and other sciences, Abu Ali became interested in medicine, reading medical books on the one hand, and treating patients on the other. In this way, at the age of sixteen, he became a doctor.

After that, he memorized the Qur'an for a year and a half, and at the age of eighteen he studied almost all the sciences of his time. "[1,101]. This method of narration is important not only to interest the reader, but also to encourage him to learn from the life of a great scientist.

In the early twentieth century, writers and critics dealt more with issues of classical literature, many of whose major works were devoted to the work of representatives of classical literature. In particular, the first critical-biographical essays were written about the representatives of classical literature. In the 1920s, S. Ayni continued the genre of critical-biographical essays initiated by Fitrat.

In Uzbek criticism, this genre developed in the 1930s, and included Ayni's Shaykhur-raisi Abu Ali ibn Sino, Olim Sharafiddinov's Alisher Navoi, and a number of other works. Scholars often draw close conclusions about the genre of the work, which enriched the biographical method, entitled "Sheikh-ur-raisi Abu Ali ibn Sina." I. Braginsky calls it "literary essays" [4,98], N. Rakhimov calls it "essays of popular scientific character" [16,38]. A. Qahhor includes such works in the list of "historical and literary essays" [1,418]. Indeed, this work belongs to the genre of critical - biographical essays. It focuses on the life and work of a great man.

RESULTS

The purpose of the critical-biographical essay is to study the biography, scientific and creative life of great people, writers and poets. On this basis, S. Ayni created the image of Ibn Sina. The author of a critical-biographical essay tries to simplify and describe to the reader the life path of Ibn Sina. To this end, he also cites his own biography. It is clear from the encyclopedic scholar's confessions that no matter how hard he tried, no matter how much he wandered around the city, he was always engaged in science, constantly studying science, writing books, creating works from various disciplines. S.Ayni writes that the 57-year-old scientist spent 18 years of his life studying science, 2 years in connection with his father's death and escape from Bukhara: "... most of the time in prison, looting and murder. He has written so much scientific work over the past thirty-seven years that no scientist in the world has been able to produce even half of what he has produced" [1,113]. In order to prove his point, he cites 77 books by Ibn Sina, citing some of Sami's Qamus al-Alam, and states that some twenty-volume books are given the same title, and that many of his treatises, poems, and many other works are not on this list. Reflecting on the contents of the book Al-Qanun, S. Ayni translates an excerpt from Ibn Sina's Encyclopaedia in detail and concludes: Abu Ali was not only envious, but also engaged in it" [1,119]. Apparently, when S.Ayni tells about the life of the great scientist, we witness that he had a great respect for his personality and creativity. I. Braginsky also said that this work of Ayni is not like any other philological work, "his essay is a bright, perfect description of a poet or a scientist, a living person." The image of Abu Ali ibn Sina in a critical-biographical essay based on an in-depth scientific analysis of the rich life and concrete evidence attracts the reader's attention with its vitality and credibility.

DISCUSSION

A critical-biographical essay consists of a set of concrete facts and scientific conclusions drawn on the basis of them. The literary scholar draws certain conclusions by scientifically generalizing the facts about the life and work of the writer through analysis, comparison, and

discussion. Although S. Ayni also gives many narrations about the great genius in the play, he mainly relies on clear, historical facts. The fact that he considered many sources in writing the work is also reflected in his attitude towards them. For instance, a Russian scholar denies that Ibn Sina went to Córdoba, taught students there, or that information about Amir Qaboos is based on reliable sources. This feature was able to ensure the compositional integrity of the work. As the author of the profile describes vital facts, as in fiction, like any artist, he chooses important aspects, the main aspects of human life and activity, his attitude to life. Based on the purpose of the genre, S. Ayni explains that the main purpose of a scientist's life is to dedicate his life to the happiness of the people, to devotion to science in spite of various obstacles. Because of the vitality, convexity, and persuasiveness of the image, I. Braginsky, an ethnographer, sometimes wrote these essays not as a study of writers who had already lived and died, but as a reminder that the master of the word was speaking to his contemporaries, peers, calling each other "alive." describes as [4.99]. The narration of Ibn Sina in the play and the mastery of the writer Ayni in relation to them are more vivid than the scholar Ayni. It is in this critical-biographical essay that the breadth of scientific and artistic thought is embodied in the scientific and vitality of his works.

CONCLUSIONS

1. A critical-biographical essay consists of a set of conclusions based on evidence, in which scientific generalizations are made through comparisons, analysis and narrations about the life and work of the genius.

2. In critical works, first, the synthesis of figurative thinking with scientific thinking; secondly, a sincere and loving approach to the work, understanding, interpretation and analysis of the uniqueness of art, deep creative research is at the forefront. Only then will a well-developed critical work be created. From this point of view, the essay accurately and truthfully reflects the life and work of Abu Ali ibn Sina. One of the main achievements of the work is the coverage of important aspects of the life and work of the scientist.

3. The emphasis in the essay on exemplary qualities for the younger generation, free, sincere thinking, respect and love for the personality of a great scientist, ensured the charm and eternity of the work. "The survival of the human soul," says Chingiz Aitmatov, "depends on the fate of a great person." Such a person always looks straight at the world, the truth, and is intolerant of ignorance and backwardness. " For this reason, the biographies and destinies of great people are studied with love. Their destiny helps to better understand human nature, the place of people in life "[22,87]. From this point of view, the critical-biographical essay dedicated to Abu Ali ibn Sina remains a work that does not lose its value over the years.

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